

DEVELOPMENT OF FLAX FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER FOR REINFORCED CONCRETE EXTERNAL STRENGTHENING

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the development of new environmentally friendly concrete reinforcement composites using technical flax fibers. Reinforcement of concrete structures through external bonding of glass or carbon fiber reinforced polymers is now approved and widely used. These FRP materials apply an additional tensile force to the concrete surface opposing the deformation and provide an extra protection layer with the environment. Flax fibers are biodegradable, cost-effective and have specific mechanical properties comparable to those of glass fibers, making them interesting in the field of composite reinforcement.

In this study two different applying methods for concrete strengthening are examined, (1) pre-hardened flax/epoxy composite strips produced by compression molding, and (2) hand-laid up flexible flax fabrics impregnated on site with ambient temperature curing epoxy resins. Several combinations of matrices and flax fabrics were tested. The composites' mechanical properties and cohesion were determined through tensile loading and delamination tests. The impregnation quality was assessed through SEM microscopy. The reinforcement ability and the adhesion on concrete substrate of the composites were evaluated through pull-out and double shear tests. Different numbers of layers and application methods were tested to determine an optimal use of the composite. The tests show good concrete/FFRP bonding and high mechanical properties, leading to concrete failures rather than in the composite or the interface. Then the durability of the composite's properties and adhesion on concrete was tested through accelerated ageing procedures. The results are very promising and flax fibers as concrete reinforcement deserve to be considered further.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to bad conception, modification of the conditions of use or simply ageing degradation, many concrete structures require reinforcement and retrofitting to stay secure. The strengthening through external bonding of glass or carbon fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) has been extensively developed in the last 20 years and proven effective [1,2]. The two most widely used application methods are the plate bonding and the wet lay-up techniques, both requiring a sizing on the concrete by a thermosetting resin curable at ambient temperature. Despite their inferior mechanical properties glass fibers are more frequently used than carbon fibers [3]. However ecological considerations justify the substitution of these synthetic glass fibers to more environmentally-friendly vegetal fibers [4, 5].

Among vegetal fibers, bast fibers have the highest mechanical properties and of those, flax presents the best potential combination of light weight, low cost, and high specific mechanical properties, comparable to glass fibers [6]. Numerous attempts to use flax as FRP reinforcement as glass substitution can be found in the literature [7, 8], however none as concrete external reinforcement. The performances of the reinforcement FRP depend directly on the properties of the individual components and on its capacity to transmit the stresses from the concrete to the reinforcement fibers. The resin must therefore have a good adhesion with the concrete as well as with the reinforcing fibers. Yet the hydrophilic nature of the flax fibers leads to poor compatibility with the hydrophobic polymer

matrices. Moreover flax fibers are not real long-fibers, but aggregated individual fibers 10 mm to 80 mm long [9], which leads to reduced mechanical properties.

The purpose of this paper is to introduce the development of a new more environmentally friendly flax FRP (FFRP) for the external strengthening of concrete structures using the hand layup technique despite these inherent difficulties. The composites' mechanical properties were determined through tensile tests. The bonding to concrete substrate and consequently its aptitude as reinforcement material was assessed through double lap shear tests.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The flax fabrics used in this study were cultivated and produced in France following the quality and traceability of ISO and NF XP T 25-501 norms specific to technical flax fibers. The flax fibers went through the four usual stages of preparation: pulling, retting, scutching, and heckling into ribbons. The ribbons have not been twisted in order to preserve the quality of the technical fibers. The quality of the final ribbon is standardized by mixing fibers from different productions years and flax varieties. The unidirectional fabrics are hold together by fine weft yarns that have been neglected in all further considerations due to the poor fabric cohesion on their direction. The bidirectional fabrics are woven in 3/3 twill offering balanced properties in both 0/90° directions.

2.2 Preparation of the composites

The pre-hardened composite were realized by an external company FIBROLINE using epoxy C. Flax fabrics UD400 are impregnated layer by layer with resin powder following their D-Preg ® technology and fixed in the fabric through calendar. The impregnated layers are piled in the same orientation and consolidated in a hot-press under 10 bars at 160°C. The composite is then glued on the concrete surface with ambient temperature curing epoxy D.

For the hand-laid composite, two bi-components epoxy resins curing at ambient temperature and commonly used in concrete strengthening have been selected. The flax fibers were impregnated with a low viscosity epoxy A and layered on a more viscous compatible epoxy resin B, enabling the composite to stick to the concrete surface. The epoxy and hardeners have been mixed at the specified ratio 33:17 for A and 7:3 for B.

Resin	ρ (kg.dm-3)	E (GPa)	σ_u (MPa)	ϵ_u (%)
Epoxy A	1.06		35	1.35
Epoxy B	1.25	2.3	27	1.7
Epoxy C	1.25	3.0	80	3.0
Epoxy D	1.30	4.5	30	0.9

Table 1. Characteristics of the used resins from producers.

Fabric	m^s (g/m ²)	Tex	Weaving	E (GPa)	σ_u (MPa)	ϵ_u (%)
S350	350	1300	Twill 3/3	32	550	1.7
S600	600	2900				
UD400	400	2900	Unidirectional			

Table 2. Characteristics of the used fabrics from producer.

2.3 Density and fiber content measurements

The composite density was measured with a Kern 573 balance. The density of hot pressed hard composite was measured using the dimensions of the plates. The density of wet layup samples was measured by hydrostatic weighing in water, and the density was calculated following Eq.(1).

$$\rho_{comp} = \rho_{air} + \frac{M_{air}}{M_{air} - M_{liq}} \cdot (\rho_{liq} - \rho_{air}) \quad (1)$$

With M_{air} and M_{liq} the measured mass of the composite respectively in the air and the liquid. The porosity volume fractions were determined by using the following Eq (2) adapted from Scida et al. (2013) [10]:

$$v_p = 1 - \frac{\rho_{comp}}{\rho_m} + \frac{n^p \cdot \rho_f^s}{h^p} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\rho_m} - \frac{1}{\rho_f} \right) \quad (2)$$

where ρ_{comp} , ρ_m and ρ_f are respectively the mass density of the composite, the matrix and the dry fibers; ρ_f^s is the areal density of the dry fabric; and n^p is the number of layers. The density of the flax fibers was fixed a $\rho_f = 1540 \text{ kg.m}^{-3}$ [11].

2.4 Observation of microstructure

The microstructure analysis helped to determine the impregnation of the flax fibers and analyze the weakness zones. After rupture through tensile traction, samples of the composite are cut out and metalized with gold/palladium before being observed with a Hitachi S800-1 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3 MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

3.1 Tensile characterization test

For the hand-laid specimens, flax fabric pieces of a length of 26 cm in the main directions are impregnated with epoxy A matrix by hand and layered in the same orientation on waxed wooden plates with a layer epoxy B reproducing the layer enabling the composite to stick to a concrete surface. The composites are scraped with a trowel to eliminate excessive resin and the air bubbles as well as possible and are left to cure in atmospheric conditions at 20°C for 7 days.

The hand-laid and pre-hardened flax composites are cut out of the composite plates, 2.5 cm x 25 cm, using a circular saw with a water cooling system and left to dry. Tensile tests on longitudinal direction were carried out following standardized static tension tests norm ISO 527-1 on a universal tensile testing machine ZWICK /1475. The tensile specimens were straightened at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min until rupture of the specimen. Tensile force was determined through force sensor and longitudinal strain with 10 mm strain gauges (120 Ω) glued to the composites specimens surface.

The ultimate strain and tensile modulus were calculated as specifies in the norm using the gross-laminated area for the pre-hardened composites and the net fiber area for the hand-laid composites as introduced by the American Concrete Institute [12]. The gross-laminated area is calculated using the total cross-sectional area of the cured composite. The net-fiber area is calculated using the known area of the fibers, neglecting the resin, since the wet layup process leads to variable resin content. As a mean to completely disregard the composites thickness, the tensile stress per composites width was also calculated (ξ_u) in kN.cm^{-1} . This value gives a clearer indication of the stress the composite could take once at the surface of concrete.

3.2 Tensile characterization results

For the hand-laid composite two series of FFRP have been made with the two fabrics S350 and S600 varying the number of folds. The hot-pressed pre-hardened composite was tested with 3 and 4 folds of UD400 fabric. Figure 1 represents the results of the tensile tests obtained for the hand-laid S600(x4) and hot-pressed UD400 (x3) FFRP. The curves are slightly dispersed, what could be a sign for some heterogeneity in the material.

All the stress-strain curves present a higher slope at small deformations as has been previously stated by many with flax fibers, both unidirectional and random mat of flax [13]. Baley et al. (2012) proposed a stress-strain model of their FFRP in tension with a nonlinear initial region that then meet a linear asymptote [14]. Scida et al. (2013) have associated this phenomenon by the reorientation of flax micro-fibrils [10]. Poilâne et al. (2014) described the stress-strain curves of FFRP as “bi-linear” with

the bending area called “yield point” and introduce the “apparent modulus” measured from the first region [15]. We decided however to measure the modulus in the second region of the curves considering it correspond more to the effective stress in the material in the structure. The hand-laid composite present a stress at rupture around 150 MPa comparable to those of some commercial wet layup glass FRP ($E_G \geq 20$ GPa; $\sigma_G \geq 150$ MPa), but a module only half as good around 12 GPa. The hot-pressed composites present mechanical properties ($E \geq 16$ GPa; $\sigma \geq 235$ MPa) similar to the one found in the literature for hot-pressed epoxy FFRP [9-10, 14-16].

Figure 1. Typical strain-stress curves in tension of the tested FFRP.

Fabric	Process	Folds	V^f (%)	V^p (%)	E (GPa)	σ_u (MPa)	ξ_u (kN/cm)	ε_u (%)
S350	hand-laid	1	10	6	9.9 ± 1.0	172 ± 9	0.84 ± 0.05	1.00 ± 0.12
		2	14	9	11.4 ± 1.5	150 ± 6	1.46 ± 0.06	1.17 ± 0.08
		3	16	11	11.4 ± 1.5	168 ± 12	2.47 ± 0.17	1.27 ± 0.03
S600	hand-laid	1	16	4	12.4 ± 3.5	130 ± 8	0.82 ± 0.05	0.97 ± 0.15
		2	19	10	16.0 ± 4.0	157 ± 12	1.98 ± 0.15	1.06 ± 0.19
		3	21	9	14.0 ± 0.9	181 ± 6	3.42 ± 0.11	1.17 ± 0.17
		4	27	10	12.9 ± 0.7	155 ± 4	3.90 ± 0.10	1.16 ± 0.06
UD400	hot-press	3	50	15	16.3 ± 0.7	240 ± 10	3.27 ± 0.40	1.17 ± 0.30
		4	50	15	20.0 ± 0.7	236 ± 8	4.72 ± 0.16	1.15 ± 0.10

Table 3. Results of the tensile tests on Flax FRP composites.

For the hand-laid composite it appears that the volumetric percentage of fibers V^f increases with the number of folds as well as the percentage of porosity V^p . The proportion of the bonding layer B decreases relative to the whole composite with the increasing number of layers. This parallel evolution supports the hypothesis that the porosity of the composite is mainly concentrated in the bundles and fibers themselves. The number of folds does not appear to impact on the stress, what can be explained through the fact that the thickness increases with the number of folds compensating the stress. We do not observe proportional relationship between the volume of fiber V^f and the strain at failure σ_u or the modulus E unlike various publications on the subject [15,17]. This difference can be due to the calculation method of the net area. As illustrated in Figure 2 the module appears relatively constant while the stress per width increases with the number of plies of composite in a quasi-proportional manner. The hand-laid S350-FFRP presents higher mechanical properties than the S600-FFRP for the

same theoretical amount of fiber (g.m^{-2}). However the use of the larger yarn enables to minimize the number of folds, and therefore the weakness points in the composite, for the same stress per width.

Figure 2. Evolution of the modulus and the stress per width with the number of folds.

3.3 Observation of the microstructure after tensile failure

Fig. 3 shows the SEM observations of the fracture surface of the hot press pre-hardened composite after the tensile test. The composite fracture surface shows steps, making it possible to recognize each of the three fiber layers Fig. 3(a). This highlights the heterogeneity of the material. However only few fibres are loosened and each layer seem to have broken as a cohesive material Fig. 3(b). Epoxy resin residues are visible until the end of the loosen fibers, which is a sign for good compatibility between the resin and the fibers Fig. 3(c). The fracture therefore happened in the matrix and not at the interface between matrix and fibers.

Fig. 3: SEM views of the fracture surface of the pre-hardened FFRP UD400 (x3).

The SEM observation of the fracture surfaces of the wet hand-laid composite (Fig. 4) shows firstly the heterogeneity of the fibers distribution. The fabric layers are clearly visible on Fig. 4(a). As shown in Fig. 4(b) the inside of the fibers bundles are easily laid bare. This is the consequence of a poor impregnation inside the bundles. Nonetheless the impregnated fibers break cohesively with the matrix. The interface between the two resins A/B, Fig. 4(c), displays no sign of fracture, which confirms their good compatibility.

Fig. 4: SEM views of the fracture surface of wet hand laid epoxy FFRP S350 (x3).

4 ADHESION CHARACTERIZATION

4.1 Double lap shear test

Previous studies showed that the comprehension of the creep phenomenon at the FRP-concrete interface is key to understand the failure mechanisms of the reinforcement [18,19]. The adherence was therefore tested with the standard double-lap shear test proposed by the Japanese Concrete Institute [20] as described by Ferrier (2011) [21].

The concrete blocks (140 mm x 140 mm x 250 mm) are cast in metal molds with a separating element in polystyrene foam of 40 mm thickness. Each block is traversed by a threaded rod of 20 mm ϕ and 250 mm length with a central bolt in order to assure the grip and enable exert the traction on the concrete blocks. The concrete is prepared according to the NF EN 18-422, and allowed to dry for at least 28 days. The concrete blocks are attached by two parallel bonded FFRP strips (Fig.5). For the wet hand-laid composite the flax fabrics strips of 460 mm x 60 mm are impregnated one by one by hand with the epoxy A and glued to the vertical concrete surface with epoxy B. The composites are scraped with a trowel to eliminate excessive resin and the air bubbles as well as possible and are left to cure in atmospheric conditions at 20°C for 7 days. For the pre-hardened composite, strips of 450 mm x 45 mm are glued on the surface with epoxy D and left to cure in atmospheric conditions at 20°C for 7 days.

Figure 5: (a) Test principle of the double lap shear test, (b) Illustration of a test, (c) Double shear test after failure in concrete

The calculations were done following the recommendations of the AUGC [22]. A tensile load of 1 mm/min is applied to the concrete blocks inducing the shear stress along the adhesive joint until failure. The test's temperature was 20°C. Strain gauges of resistance 120 Ω on the surface of the FRP enable to measure its deformation the central part of each strip and along the central axis of one of them. Two LVDT displacement sensors (10⁻⁴ mm precision) measure the distance between the blocs at each sides of the interval (ΔL₁). The increase of this distance is due to the composite elongation (ΔL₂) and the slip between the FRP and the concrete support, see Figure 3. The average slip (γ) of the two lap joints is calculated from Eq.(3), by dividing the slip displacement by the joints thickness (s).

$$\gamma = \frac{\Delta L_1 - \Delta L_2}{s} \quad (3)$$

The average shear stress (τ_{ave}) is calculated by dividing the applied force (F) by the bonded surface area (A_{adh}); and the global shear modulus (G) following Eq.(4):

$$G = \frac{\tau_{ave}}{\gamma} = \frac{F/A_{adh}}{\gamma} \quad (4)$$

The local deformation τ in the composite strips is followed with deformations gauges along the composite strips and is calculated following Eq. (5) with Δε_f the deformation of the composite, t_f the thickness of the composite, E_f the modulus of the composite, Δx the distance between two gauges. The origin is situated at the center of the two blocks. Gauges were placed at 0 - 1 - 4 - 7 - 12 cm from the origin on the middle line of the strip.

$$\tau = \frac{\Delta F}{b_f \cdot \Delta x} = \frac{E_f \cdot \Delta \varepsilon_f \cdot b_f \cdot t_f}{b_f \cdot \Delta x} = E_f \cdot \frac{\Delta \varepsilon_f \cdot t_f}{\Delta x} \quad (5)$$

4.2 Results of the double lap shear tests

For the wet hand-laid process, preliminary tests using hand laid S350 FRP with an increasing number of folds showed that four folds, i.e. ~3 kNcm⁻¹, were necessary to obtain a clear failure in the concrete and not in the composite. Consequently four tests with three folds of hand-laid S600 FRP were carried out. The four tests lead to a failure in the concrete, pulling out the corner of the concrete block base as displayed in Figure 6. The hand-laid composite material therefore presents mechanical properties sufficient to be used for concrete strengthening. The pre-hardened composite gave a similar response; the results are summarized in Table 4.

Figure 6. Mechanical shear behavior of the concrete-FFRP interface (with S600 x3 FRP).

	Ultimate shear stress τ_u (MPa)	Ultimate shear strain γ_u (%)	Elastic shear stress τ_e (MPa)	Elastic shear strain γ_e (%)	Elastic shear modulus G_e (GPa)
S600(x3) - FFRP hand laid	1.22 ± 0.10	1.4 ± 0.3	0.36 ± 0.09	0.03 ± 0.01	1.2 ± 0.3
UD400(x3) - FFRP hot press	1.42 ± 0.02	3.0 ± 0.6	0.36 ± 0.04	0.02 ± 0.01	2.6 ± 0.6

Table 4. Results of the double lap shear tests FFRP. (Average on four specimens for the hand-laid composite and two specimens for the hot-press composite.)

The shear behavior of the FFRP/concrete interface is characterized by a non-linear law with an initial linear domain. The first point (γ_e, τ_e) marks the limit of the elastic behavior. The second point (γ_u, τ_u) corresponds to the failure of the specimen. Between these points the adhesive joint follows a complex non-linear behavior. According to Meaud et al. (2011) the linear creep stress limits depends primarily on the properties of the polymeric matrix and consequently on the test temperature [18]. The lower the glass transition temperature T_G the lower the mechanical properties. Indeed the elastic creep limits of hand-laid and pre-hardened Flax FRP are similar to hand-laid carbon FRP reinforced concrete [21]. With a failure in the concrete, and not in the composite, the ultimate shear stress τ_u depends directly on the concrete's properties. The ultimate shear strain however appears to differ for each composite type. The ultimate shear strain of the pre-hardened composite ($\gamma_{hot-press} = 3.0\%$) is twice as important the ultimate shear strain of hand laid composite ($\gamma_{hand-laid} = 1.4\%$) which is himself at least three times higher than for CFRP. This can be directly related to the high deformability of the FFRP material compared to CFRP and to the resins properties, see Table 1.

Figure 7. Evolution of the local strain in the composite strips with the distance from the origin.

The local deformation in the composite strips was followed with deformations gauges. As can be seen in the two graphics in Fig.7 the deformation increases with tensile force applied to the blocks, and is at its highest at the center part of the strip at distance à-2 cm from the origin. The deformation then decreases along the strip. It is also important to notice that the strain at 12 cm from the origin is still negligible for the highest applied force, corresponding to the force at failure. It can be deduced that the 200 mm length of the strips used for the test is sufficient to observe the concrete reinforcement properly and that even a length of 150 mm would have been enough to get the full tensile strength of the composite.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Flax fibers are biodegradable, cost-effective and have specific mechanical properties comparable to those of glass fibers, making them interesting as glass substitution as RC external reinforcement composite. Two types of composites have been developed; pre-hardened Epoxy Flax FRP manufactured by hot pressing in a mold, and wet laid up Epoxy Flax FRP realized on site. The characterization in tension of the composite revealed a stress-strain curve similar to those already described in the literature for flax composite with a higher initial slope. The values obtained for the mechanical properties in tension for the pre-hardened FFRP ($E \geq 16$ GPa; $\sigma \geq 235$ MPa) were comparable to those found in the literature for hot-pressed epoxy FFRP. The hand-laid composite present a stress at rupture around 150 MPa comparable to those of some commercial wet layup glass FRP ($E_G \geq 20$ GPa; $\sigma_G \geq 150$ MPa), but a module only half as good around 12 GPa. Both composite have a good adhesion with the concrete substrate and induce a failure in the concrete in the double lap shear adhesion test.

The investigation of the influence of the number of fabric layers on the properties of wet laid up FFRP have shown that the tensile stress increases proportionally to the number of layers whereas modulus and strain seem quite constant. This is a good and important fact for enabling reinforcement design calculations. The evolution of the yield point and the modulus will have to be investigated further. This work is a first step to the development of a new externally bonded flax FRP material for a RC reinforcement. The first results are promising in view of the difficulty to get repeatable results coming from the biological nature of the fibers and the wet layup process. A set of shear adhesion tests and accelerated ageing tests are expected to confirm the potential of this material.

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